

STATIONARY FORESTRY CHIPPER FOR OLIVE PRUNING HARVESTING

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ABSTRACT: Olive pruning could represent an important biomass resource for energy production considering that over 2600 Gg of dry matter represent the annual amount of biomass that could be obtained from olive groves just in Italy. Different experiences of pruning harvesting are reported in literature, especially related to shredders towed by tractors while limited knowledge is available on performance, quality of work and costs of harvesting logistics based on stationary chippers. The aim of the present paper is to analyze machine performance of a forestry stationary chipper applied to pruning harvesting for what concerning work productivity, quality of the comminuted product and harvesting operating costs. Although widely used in the forestry sector, the use of a stationary chipper for harvesting and comminuting olive tree pruning is poorly documented and therefore the study is innovative and fills a gap in the literature where little information is currently available. The results showed highest work productivity ever found in olive pruning harvesting systems and equal to $5.23 \pm 0.81 \text{ Mg}_{\text{dm}} \text{ h}^{-1}$. This allowed also to obtain a little economic gain from a residue which is actually considered a problem for olive groves' owners and not a potential source of income. According to preliminary data the use of a stationary chipper seemed very efficient in olive groves with big amount of pruning to be processed, and with big branches not harvestable by the most common towed pruning harvester. In addition, the collection system based on a stationary chipper does not require pre-harvest raking. This aspect represents an added benefit in terms of cost reduction for the farmer.

Keywords: work productivity; costs analysis; harvesting system; biomass supply chain; bioenergy

1 INTRODUCTION

Olive orchards in Europe, which require regular pruning operation each 1-3 years, generate a substantial amount of residues, in the range of $1\text{-}5 \text{ Mg ha}^{-1}$ [1]. These residues can represent an important source of biomass for energetic purposes [2,3]. On the other hand, effective bioenergy production from pruning residues is still not common in Europe [4]. The major issue to be solved for the effective development of a pruning supply chain is the development of an effective harvesting and transport logistic [5,6]. Several machineries are available for pruning harvesting, the major part of these consists of modified mulchers, towed shredders or balers [7]. All these harvesting systems require a preliminary raking operation, which can account for a substantial part of the overall harvesting costs [8]. An interesting approach, generally applied in forestry sector, consists of a stationary chipper [9,10]. This system allows for avoiding the raking operation, and moreover can be applied in steeper slope in comparison to usual towed shredders [5]. A stationary chipper for pruning harvesting is currently applied by the Italian company *Ligna* (Calimera, Apulia Region, Italy), *Ligna* is an enterprise dedicated for procuring the pruning biomass produced by the olive groves located into nine municipalities around *Fiusis*, which is a 1 MWe biomass power plant, located in Apulia, which transforms it into electricity [11]. Considering the unusuality and potentiality of a stationary chipper for pruning harvesting, the aim of the present work was to assess the working performance of the system.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Study area and harvesting system description

Experimental field, of about 2.50 ha, was located in

the Carpignano Salentino Municipality (Apulia Region, Italy). The average slope was 2% with a planting layout of 12 m x 12 m. The pruning yield in the experimental field was very high, i.e. $8.96 \text{ Mg}_{\text{dm}} \text{ ha}^{-1}$.

Pruning residues were previously collected and piled on the field side by a 66-kW tractor equipped with fork (Figure 1).

Figure 1: tractor equipped with fork for the pruning accumulation near the stationary chipper.

Near the pile, a stationary chipper was located. This was powered by a Diesel motor of 129 kW able to shred wooden materials up to diameters of 45 cm (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Stationary chipper Caravaggi and tractor with uploading equipment.

The feeding of the chipper was provided by a hydraulic powered by a 129-kW tractor. Comminuted biomass was heaped on the pile and then loaded by a 90-kW lifter into the dumpster of a truck in order to be shipped to the biomass plant (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Handling of the hog fuel to be transported to the power plant.

2.1 Work productivity and costs assessment

Evaluation of working times were carried out according to the methodology proposed by Reith et al. [12]. Subsequently, measured time were used as input data to assess work productivity. In particular Theoretical Field Capacity (TFC ha h^{-1}), Effective Field Capacity (EFC ha h^{-1}) and Material Capacity (MC $\text{Mg}_{\text{dm}} \text{h}^{-1}$). Field Efficiency (FE %) was calculated as the ratio between EFC and TFC. Finally, costs per surface unit (€ ha^{-1}) and biomass unit ($\text{€ Mg}_{\text{dm}}^{-1}$) were calculated through the CRPA methodology [13].

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Results of work productivity evaluation of the investigated system are reported in Table I. The first aspect highlighted by the present findings is the very high FE of this harvesting system. This is a very interesting finding, considering that delay times are instead substantial in the major part of the other pruning's harvesting systems [14]. Regarding MC, which is another key parameter, the productivity obtained during the tests is comparable to previous similar studies regarding mobile chippers. In fact, literature findings showed a material capacity of $6.01 \text{ Mg}_{\text{fm}} \text{h}^{-1}$ for a self-propelled harvester and $6.77 \text{ Mg}_{\text{fm}} \text{h}^{-1}$ for a tractor-mounted machine [15]. Tests conducted with towed chippers showed much lower results than those observed with the stationary chipper, in particular: $1.37 \text{ Mg}_{\text{fm}} \text{h}^{-1}$ for the Promagri 2000; $0.69 \text{ Mg}_{\text{fm}} \text{h}^{-1}$ for the Jounes Atila; $1.27 \text{ Mg}_{\text{fm}} \text{h}^{-1}$ for the Serrat Olipack T1800 and $1.38 \text{ Mg}_{\text{fm}} \text{h}^{-1}$ for the Berti Picker C180 [16].

Regarding costs harvesting systems based on a stationary chipper showed high costs per surface unit (230.38 € ha^{-1}), mostly related to the several machineries needed for the implementation of the harvesting operations. On the other hand, the high MC led to low harvesting costs per biomass unit, i.e. $19.07 \text{ € Mg}_{\text{fm}}^{-1}$. Therefore costs per biomass unit are lower than the ones reported in previous similar studies on different harvesting systems [14,17].

Table I: Work productivity analysis results.

Parameter	M.U.	Value
Theoretical Field Capacity (TFC)	ha h^{-1}	0.61 ± 0.13
Effective Field Capacity (EFC)	ha h^{-1}	0.60 ± 0.13
Field efficiency (FE)	%	99.00
Material Capacity (MC)	$\text{Mg}_{\text{dm}} \text{h}^{-1}$	5.23 ± 0.81

4 CONCLUSIONS

Summarizing, a stationary chipper as a pruning harvesting system represents an interesting solution; mostly, in olive groves characterized by high biomass yields and also substantial slope. Our analysis reported very high work productivity in comparison to previous similar studies on different machineries and harvesting systems. Such high productivity led to low hog fuel production cost, referred to as the biomass unit ($\text{€ Mg}_{\text{fm}}^{-1}$). Therefore, the analyzed harvesting systems allowed to obtain also a small economic gain from pruning, which is currently considered more a problem than a possible resource.

5 REFERENCES

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6 ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The work was performed in the framework of the AGROENER project (D.D. n. 26329, 1 April 2016) funded by the Italian Ministry of Agriculture (MiPAAF). The ideas expressed do not represent either those of the European Commission or the Italian Ministry of Agriculture (MiPAAF).